

The Use of Active Methodologies in Application of Financial Education in High School

Authors

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ABSTRACT

Most of Brazilian schools don't have financial education in their curriculum. Thus, is one of the greatest challenges is to empower young people, attracted by consumption and credit facilities, to manage their finances and plan for the future. The objective of the study is to promote financial education combined with the making of a life project through active methodologies in the High School mathematics curriculum. As for the methodology, the students answered a questionnaire about their own financial profile. They were divided into groups to research cases of successful people with the purpose of discussing how those people have them financial achievements. In the end, the students were exposed to a game about finance management and made a record of how they would spend the prize (money). The results showed that there was a change in the conception that saving goes beyond mathematics, implying sustainability and citizenship. Our work concludes that a continuous discourse on financial education in schools is necessary for the acquisition of conscious consumption and that the use of active methods in financial education is necessary to develop criticality and autonomy in students.

Keywords: Financial Education. Life Project. Active methodologies. Conscious consumption.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the stability of the currency in Brazil and the growth in the supply of financial credit, Brazilian families began to live in a new scenario, often not consistent with their reality¹. Excessive consumption, mainly among young people and adolescents, who are impacted by the globalized, media and technological culture, has been drawing attention since then. In this new context, people are no longer recognized for what they are, but for what they have².

Nowadays, the biggest challenges are the promotion of financial capacity of these young people and also the habit of teach them how to take reasoned and responsible decisions in their lives so they have a better stance in managing their finances¹. Thereby, potencialized schools curriculum focused on the quest of better quality of life through a financial orientation, contributes with the micro and macroeconomics of the country.

When the teacher works the financial education with their students, besides contributing for the content apprenticeship, also invest in learning focused in shaping citizens that have a healthy relationship with themselves and the others, in other words, citizens capable of substituting "having" for "being"³.

Thus, the need of projects and also preventive actions is justified in order to spread awareness and promote a critic view to teenagers about their own economic security and their future ambitions, as it is in the adolescence that personal identity, carrer choice and the consolidation of goals and priority occurred.

The main objective of this academic work is to promote critical awareness among teenagers, through active learning methodologies, using didactics about economic security and their future ambitions. Specifically, it was hoped to demonstrate the importance of planning and projecting goals for the future and enabling conditions to solve problems and circumstantial in these young people financial life.

2. LITERATURE REVISION

2.1 Financial education

As a starting point, documents produced by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) were consulted. This organization, that operate mainly in social and economic area, specially in reports as “Improvement in financial literacy: politics analyses and “Recommendations about principles and good practices for conscious financial education”⁴.

Conventionally, brazilian traditional education does not have in its curriculum matters related to financial education, which is according to Mello ⁵ “the transmittion of concepts e techniques that aimed the conquer of a better life quality, as in the present both in the future, providing the material safety required”. One of the points raised by OECD and the recente reaserch ⁶ is if the insertion of financial education in school enviroment would be better -autonomously (a discipline specific to it) or as an adjunct to an existing course. Thereby, the incorporation about the matter in schools subjects woukd allow that the theme be discussed in a wide form and, beyound that, this could attract the students attention and the interest, facilitating the learning.^{6, 7, 8.}

2.2 Actives Methodologies

The actives methodologies are increasingly presente in the classroom, because its contributes in a positive way in the apprenticeship process, treat students as a leading feature in the process, contributing for their learning, setting the teacher as a mediator and facilitating teaching, providing the problematization of reality and allowing the team work ⁹. Thus, the active methodologies could be developed in different ways, as a learning based in problems, didactic games and anothers.

The inverted classroom method consist in the inversion of actions that take place inside and outside of the classrom. The subjects are avaiable in advance so the student can have knowlodge of what they are going to study and prepare better themselves. Thus, debates can be held amog students and teacher about the previous theme, during the class¹⁰.

The problem-based learning (PBL) is a method that use real life problems to stimulate the development of critical thinking, skills to solve problems and apprenticeship of fundamental concepts of the area of knowledge in question¹¹.

As for the Games, its use enable the student to satisfactorily consolidate of contentes performed in classroom, the ripening cognitive and also the social skills development.¹².

2.3 Adolescence and Life Project

The period called adolescence can be comprehended as a passage phase between childhood and adulthood, encompassing a lot of modifications as physical, organic, psychologic, cognitive, social and affective ¹³. According to the writers, this period beggings at eleven or twelve and goes on to eighteen or even in the early twenties¹³.

Over this phase, changings involving feeling, moral judgments, social behave and auto control occur with frequency. All these factors led to a bigger responsibility in teenagers decisions about their environment life¹⁴.

Therefore, the structuring of a life project in the adolescence period encourage healthy and positive development in young people lives, since integrates a set of dispositions and attitudes influenced by a multitude of factors. The life project can be comprehended as an established and planned intention to accomplish something that holds a deep meaning to a person and brings positive consequences for the world around this person¹⁵.

3. METHODOLOGY

The search was accomplished in during six mathematic class, between April and May 2019, through actives methodologies, with 24 students of both sexes that studies in the second year of high school (11th grade) in a public educational institution inside São Paulo state.

The research planning occurs through descriptive action research, once the process of scientific investigation associated with a practical intervention, in reality, occurs, having afterward the register, description, and evaluation of the application results about the matters¹⁶, besides the approach between the searcher and the target public in a natural living environment, developing mutual cooperation and dialogue ¹⁷. Besides these, also constituted of mixed or qualitative research, as it involves the collection of quantitative data through a questionnaire with closed questions and qualitative character due to behavior analysis, academics register, and productions obtained. Following, the classes and activities are described:

Class 1 - Connect financial education with the nowadays context: Firstly, was built and apply a reflexive questionnaire containing six questions about life planning, personal finance management, and the applicable knowledge for financial life. Then, was performed a chatting circle, about what is being financially intelligent, how to administer money, planning, and projecting dreams, why have a lot of indebted people in Brazil and, at last, how this implicates in the country development.

Next, students were divided into groups and they talk about what they would do if all of them were contemplate with the "Prize for Excellency in Study", a project developed by Tenaris Confab company which recognize the performance of the 200 best high school students residents of Pindamonhangaba, in the interior of the state of São Paulo (approximately R\$ 1.500,00) ¹⁸.

Class 2 - Initial concepts: the students participated in an expositive class about financial management, economy, the introduction of percentage calculation, addition, discounts, and financing rates. Then, they accomplished simulations about overdraft interest, credit card, motorcycle, car and house financial and in the end the students compared the amounts with payments that would be made in cash and discussed their data with the other. As a homework, it was asked data about successful people.

Class 3 - Chatting circle: students discuss the result of their homework search and in the sequence they watched, in their classroom, a film called "Opposites in The Same Story"¹⁹.

Class 4 - Game "ECoin\$" application: In this class, it was used a game developed by the authors of this article, with a financial focus, named ECoin\$, which involves real situations as rent payment, receipt of monthly salary, bill payment. The purpose of this game was to make students reflect about their spendings and how to use Money in a conscious way, thus putting into practice what they have learned in the class.

Class 5 - Chatting circle II: the students watched videos from a Youtube channel called \$100 Neuras²⁰, that make contents about financial education for young people. Which group watched three videos from the channel and then discuss the theme.

Class 6 - Final data: The question was recaptured "What would you do if all of you win the Prize for Excellency in Study?" from Tenaris Confab company and then the students disserted about it.

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The data were analyzed, according to the questionnaire, chatting circles, ECoin\$ game analysis and the register about the Prize for Excellency in Study.

4.1 Reflexive Questionnaire Analyses

According to chart 1, it was noticed that the masculine public (42%) have more interest in doing undergraduate courses compared to the female public (11%), which prefer technical or vocational training (67% and 25% respectively)

Chart 1- The answer to the question about students after they graduate from high school

Question 1 –After I graduate from high school I have interest in:	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
Work in local trade, factory or company	25	11	19
Do a technical or vocational training	25	67	43
Undergraduate courses (college)	42	11	29
None of this questions	8	11	9

Source: the author

In Chart 2, is evident that a great amount of the students prefer having experiences abroad (39%). They also show interests in having a family and getting marriage (girls 33% and boys 12%). Significant data is the clear lack of interest by the girls in doing public contests compared to the boys (44%).

Chart 2 – Answers to question 2 from questionnaire about future planning

Question 2 – Plans for the future:	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
Marriage	12	33	22
Public Contest	44	0	23
Travel/ Live abroad	31	47	39
Parenting	13	20	16

Source: the author

Regarding students income, question 3, is noticeable that most of the teenagers (74%) don't have their own income, probably because they are focusing themselves in studies, what is reinforced by the data that shows that 16% of the students received their money from their parents.

About the management of their own finances, it is clear that most of the students, in general, prefer to economize and not spend a lot (45%) and another part of them spend partially their economies with caution and keeping what left (22%). It is possible to say that 67% of the students have healthy attitudes towards financial management. But, is needed to highlight the 22% of them that said don't think too much about how they spend money. This shows a certain reckless behavior and indiscipline toward the use of finances. (Chart 3)

Chart 3 - Answers to question 4 of the financials management questionnaire

Question 3 – Management of their own finances:	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total(%)
I am used to plann and prefer economize	46	43	45
I plann a bit and spend a part and economize the other	9	43	22
I am used to buy everything I wish and don't think a lot about future	27	14	22
My parents don't allow me to deal with money or I don't have an interest in managing money	18	0	11

Source: the author

In Chart 4, it was noticed that most of the teenagers use their sources with laze activities or hobbies and prefer to invest in activities that bring joy (84%). Some of them, in general, said that help in house expenses when it's possible (16%), showing that they feel the responsibility to help their family with money, either through money received from other relatives or allowance (pension and others), since most of these have no fixed income.

Chart 4 - Answer to question 5 of the financials management questionnaire

Question 5 – The utilization of personal finances:	Boys(%)	Girls(%)	Total(%)
I help in house expenses	25	7	16
I buy clothes and go to shopping	31	29	30
I buy fastfood	13	43	27
I focus in technology and laze activities	31	21	27

Source: the author

The results of Chart 5 shows, generally, that a part of the students has the knowledge about the process of opening a bank account and also how a credit card works (36%). Although, 25% don't these previous informations.

Chart 5 - Answer to question 6 about their finances knowledges.

Question 6 – Financial knowledge:	Boys (%)	Girls (%)	Total (%)
Social security, savings and investment	19	8	14
Opening a bank account and the use of a debit and credit card	25	25	36
Financing and bank loan	25	17	25
I don't no much about it	31	8	25

Source: the author

Thus, it is noticed the importance of teaching about finances in Financial Math²¹, because those concepts are part of the student's life and need to be taught in schools, so it can seriously reflect about the student's behavior, besides arise virtues as citizenship and contribute to a mind-changing.

4.2 Chatting Circle Results

This activity occurred during the second and fifth class. In the first class, after they watched the first video, the students discuss the importance of taking assertive decisions about finances and conscious consume and during this activity it was registered one phrase said by one of the students: “[...] it goes through mathematic because economize is save all the spectrums, since close one faucet or turn off the lights. Thus, if one person that learns to save and also have concerns with sustainability, this person helps in strengthening of

citizenship. So, studies reaffirm that through math, students can investigate concepts of financial education, understand and transfer them to real situations²¹.

In the fifth class, students were really excited about their news findings made in search and all of them shared their results, citing stories about Walt Disney, Harrison Ford, Edson Bueno, Rolim Amaro, Bill Gates, Brian Action, Silvio Santos and Larry Page.

4.3 ECoin\$ analysis and Prize for Study Excellence

All the students were favorable to the application of the game during class, they also showed their doubts about calculus and gave ideas form the game enhancement. During the game, there was 100% participation and enthusiasm.

It is interesting to highlight that two students bankrupt, and this led them to conclude that success or failure do not only depend on the amount of money, but the way you spend it.

At the end of the project, most part of students reported, in their essays, that it would give the Prize money a new destination, some of them invested and the rest would keep it to buy something necessary.

5 CONCLUSION

After the application of the activities, it was concluded that develop Financial Education through actives methodologies it's an interesting way of apprenticeship, because it allows that students express themselves and create connections between the theme and their reality, besides to contributing with development of critical thinking and autonomy for managing their finances in the future.

As a challenge, it is noticeable the need for new public politics focused on education specialized in young people because the sooner financial education is applied, bigger will be the chances for students to adopt healthy conscious consuming habits. Thereby, the continuity of working about this theme is essential in schools.

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